

Comparative Outcomes of Phacoemulsification versus Manual Small-Incision Surgery in Posterior Polar Cataracts: A Retrospective Analysis

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Abstract:

This one-year retrospective study compared phacoemulsification and MSICS in 100 posterior polar cataract patients at Patna Medical College and Hospital. We found that phacoemulsification minimises posterior capsule rupture risk and speeds vision recovery compared to MSICS. Both methods improved postoperative visual acuity, although phacoemulsification achieved 20/40 vision faster. MSICS is cost-efficient in resource-limited situations, while phacoemulsification is safer and more effective for posterior polar cataracts. These findings show that surgical technique selection should incorporate patient-specific characteristics and resource availability.

Keywords: Phacoemulsification, Manual Small-Incision Cataract Surgery, Posterior Polar Cataracts, Visual Recovery

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Introduction

The most effective treatment for cataracts, which are the primary cause of blindness globally, is still cataract surgery [1]. The position of posterior polar cataracts and the posterior capsule's inherent fragility make them particularly difficult to treat. These variables raise the possibility of intraoperative problems, especially posterior capsule rupture, which might have a major effect on the result of the surgery. This means that the surgical strategy to be employed must be carefully considered [2,3].

Two commonly used methods for extracting cataracts are phacoemulsification and manual small-incision cataract surgery (MSICS) [4]. Phacoemulsification is preferred due to its low invasiveness and quick recovery after surgery. It is defined by the use of an ultrasonic probe to emulsify the lens before aspiration. On the other hand, MSICS is renowned for its affordability and usefulness in environments with limited resources because it requires a smaller incision and does not require phacoemulsification equipment [5,6].

Choosing the right surgical approach is essential, particularly in complex instances like posterior polar cataracts. In patients with posterior polar cataracts, in particular, this retrospective study compares the results of phacoemulsification with MSICS with an emphasis on intraoperative complications, postoperative visual acuity, and recovery timeframes. Through the analysis of these results, this study aims to improve patient care in various clinical settings by offering evidence-based

recommendations on the best surgical strategy for addressing this complicated problem.

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective study compared posterior polar cataract surgery outcomes with phacoemulsification and MSICS. The goal was to compare intraoperative problems, postoperative visual acuity, and recovery durations between these two surgical procedures.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, encompassing a period from March 1, 2023, to March 1, 2024.

Participants: A total of 100 posterior polar cataract patients were studied. Patients over 40 with posterior polar cataracts appropriate for surgery were eligible. Patients with glaucoma, retinal disorders, or previous ocular surgeries were excluded because they potentially affect surgical outcomes or visual recovery.

Data Collection: Demographic information, preoperative ocular assessments, type of surgery (phacoemulsification or MSICS), intraoperative complications, postoperative visual acuity at various time points, and postoperative complications were extracted from eligible patients' medical records. The key outcomes were posterior capsule rupture during surgery and visual acuity improvement one day, one week, and one month after surgery.

Surgical Techniques: Phacoemulsification: A conventional machine was used with a clean corneal incision and intraocular lens implantation. Manual Small-Incision Cataract Surgery (MSICS): A smaller, self-sealing scleral tunnel incision is followed by manual expression lens extraction and intraocular lens implantation.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The chi-square test was used for categorical data comparison, and the student's t-test was employed for continuous variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using SPSS software, version 25.

Results

100 patients with posterior polar cataracts were enrolled in the study, 50 of whom had MSICS and 50 of whom underwent phacoemulsification surgery. The patients were evenly split between the two surgical groups. The participants' average age was sixty years old, and both groups' gender distribution was equal. Comparability between the groups was ensured by the similar preoperative visual acuities and concomitant states of all the patients. When it comes to posterior polar cataract surgery, the rate of posterior capsule rupture—which is a major concern—was considerably lower in the phacoemulsification group as opposed to the

MSICS group. In particular, 16% of patients receiving MSICS and 4% of patients undergoing phacoemulsification experienced posterior capsule rupture ($p=0.03$). Improvements in visual acuity were measured one day, one week, and one month after surgery. When compared to preoperative levels, both groups' visual acuity significantly improved. In contrast to the MSICS group (72% attaining 20/40 or better), the phacoemulsification group (90% achieving 20/40 or better) showed a quicker recovery of visual acuity at the one-day postoperative mark. Over 95% of patients in each group achieved a visual acuity of 20/40 or better at one month following surgery, indicating identical visual outcomes for both groups.

Individuals who underwent phacoemulsification reported quicker recovery times and reduced incidence of postoperative inflammation. Patients reported going back to their regular activities in an average of one week, and the use of anti-inflammatory medicine was decreased. The MSICS group, on the other hand, reported a marginally longer recovery time and a greater need for postoperative care. For categorical variables, the chi-square test and for continuous variables, the Student's t-test, verified the statistical significance of the differences between the two groups' rates of posterior capsule rupture and early postoperative visual recovery.

Table 1: This table summarizes the comparative outcomes, highlighting the advantages of phacoemulsification in terms of lower complication rates and faster recovery times.

Variable	Phacoemulsification	MSICS
Patients (n)	50	50
Mean Age (years)	60	60
Posterior Capsule Rupture (%)	4%	16%
Visual Acuity 20/40 or better at 1 Day Post-op (%)	90%	72%
Visual Acuity 20/40 or better at 1 Week Post-op (%)	95%	88%
Visual Acuity 20/40 or better at 1 Month Post-op (%)	98%	95%
Postoperative Inflammation	Lower	Higher
Return to Normal Activities (days)	7 days	10 days

Discussion

The results of this retrospective analysis highlight notable variations in manual small-incision cataract surgery (MSICS) and phacoemulsification outcomes for patients with posterior polar cataracts [7]. The precision and safety of the phacoemulsification technique is critical in controlling the fragile posterior capsule associated with this form of cataract. This is evidenced by the decreased incidence of posterior capsule rupture in the phacoemulsification group (4% versus 16% in MSICS) [8,9]. This is in line with other research that indicates the phacoemulsification-controlled

environment lessens mechanical stress on the capsule during surgery [10].

Furthermore, the phacoemulsification group's quick recovery of visual acuity may have been made possible by the low surgical stress and sophisticated optical coherence of the intraocular lenses employed in this procedure [11,12]. One day following surgery, patients should be able to obtain 90% of 20/40 vision or greater, since this can greatly improve patient satisfaction and lessen the need for postoperative care [13]. This is especially crucial in situations where resources for follow-up are scarce. But it's important to take into account

MSICS's wider relevance, particularly in low-resource areas where phacoemulsification's cost and availability can be prohibitive. Because of its affordability and efficacy in enhancing visual outcomes, MSICS is still a desirable surgical option, despite its longer recovery periods and greater rates of complications [14,15,16].

The comparative methodology of this work offers insightful information about the strategic selection of surgical methods based on resource- and patient-specific factors [17]. Long-term results and patient-reported happiness and quality of life after surgery should be the main topics of future research, as these topics were outside the purview of this one. In particular, in different healthcare contexts, such data could further inform clinical judgments and policy-making in the field of ophthalmic care [18–20].

Conclusion

This retrospective analysis showed that, for patients with posterior polar cataracts, phacoemulsification provides better results than manual small-incision cataract surgery (MSICS) in terms of reduced rates of intraoperative problems and faster visual recovery. Even though both surgical methods were successful in increasing visual acuity, phacoemulsification turned out to be the better option because of its improved safety profile and quick recovery after surgery. These results imply that the best method for treating posterior polar cataracts should be given preference when phacoemulsification is possible. The necessity for a customised strategy based on the available resources and patient needs is shown by the function that MSICS plays as an affordable substitute in settings with limited resources.

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